

Improving the Quality of Wind Field Reconstruction Techniques for Lidar-assisted Control of Wind Turbines

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1 Introduction

The response of a wind turbine to changes in the wind speed is traditionally achieved via a feedback blade pitch and generator torque control. Conventional control system can only react after the wind changes impact the turbine.

Light detection and ranging (lidar) technology measuring the wind in front of the rotor gives the wind turbine the ability to respond to emerging wind dynamics prior to its occurring. However, commercial application remains limited so far, although the potential for improvements in control performance has been shown in literature [5], indicating the need for further research.

Thinking about lidar for control applications, the challenge is to take advantage of the potential of lidar technology taking into account the technological trade-offs. Lidar makes use of the Doppler effect and therefore is restricted by temporal and spatial limitations: By concept, lidar detects the velocity of particles along the beam, the radial or so-called line-of-sight wind speed, and is unaware of the actual wind flow dynamics [1]. By design, current lidar systems are only covering limited points over the rotor disk due to their scan methods (rotating prisms, fixed telescopes) and need to average over a certain time to provide reliable signals. To take advantage of remote sensing for lidar-assisted control of wind turbines, a technique for reconstructing the wind field from the measured data is needed. For that purpose, one needs a closure about the wind field dynamics that can be used to approximate the unavailable data based on the available ones.

The wind field is mostly reconstructed with known parameters (i.e. scan configuration) and assuming static wind models (e.g. homogeneous flow or perfect alignment). Several measurements are usually combined and the wind field is reconstructed using the least-squares method [2]. While these methods already have been successfully applied to real measurements, using dynamic models and advanced methods are promising to improve the quality of the wind field reconstruction (WFR) and by this increasing the benefit of lidar-assisted control.

Addressing the broader question of data-driven approaches versus first-principle approaches in fluid mechanics, [3] note that flows, particularly high Reynolds number atmospheric flows, require consideration of nonlinearities and multiple spatiotemporal scales that are difficult to capture with data-driven approaches, while first-principle approaches are usually computationally too slow for real-time control. Therefore, reducing the complexity of first-principle approaches it is important to explore.

Here, a promising approach using a dynamic wind model is developed in [6], reconstructing the 2D wind field between two nacelle-based lidar beams. The authors derive a simplified Large Eddy Simulation (LES) model by applying scale analysis to the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations. Using model-based state estimation techniques, the model incorporates the history of lidar measurements into current and future estimates of the wind field. To reduce the error between actual and estimated wind fields, in a recursive fashion, an unscented Kalman filter [7] is used.

This work is therefore intended to contribute to the development of lidar technology by improving the wind preview quality.

Figure 1: The basic framework to test and evaluate wind field reconstruction methods.

2 Methods

In this work we develop a framework which allows to test and evaluate wind field reconstruction methods for lidar-assisted control.

The basic structure of the framework is presented in Figure 1 and consists of following blocks:

- 1 Wind Field Generator (providing the reference wind field).
- 2 Lidar Simulator (simulates a Lidar that provides raw lidar measurements from the reference wind field).
- 3 Wind Field Reconstruction (reconstructs the wind field from lidar measurement and provides the estimated rotor-effective wind speed)
- 4 Evaluation (evaluates the quality of the reconstructed wind field comparing it to the reference wind field).

The framework allows to use different representations for each block. We developed following 2D testing strategy:

- 1 Baseline 2D WFR in nominal environment: Here we used TurbSim [4] for the wind field generator, a simple lidar simulator using a point model, and a baseline WFR assuming perfect alignment, providing the rotor-effective wind speed (REWS). The wind field is evaluated comparing the REWS from the reference wind field to the estimated one. First results are described below.
- 2 Baseline 2D WFR in LES environment: Here, the above method is applied to a full LES wind field. We expect a lower wind preview quality than in the first step.
- 3 Advanced 2D WFR based on simplified LES and Kalman filter in nominal environment: Here, we will test the approach of [6] in its nominal environment, generating a wind field with the simplified LES.
- 4 Advanced 2D WFR based on simplified LES and Kalman filter in LES environment: Here, the above method is applied to a full LES wind field. Here we expect a lower preview quality than in the third step, but a higher one compared to the second step.

3 Results

This section presents the results for the baseline 2D WFR in nominal environment, the first step in our testing strategy. The presented case study employs a IEA Kaimal wind field as a reference and a two-point lidar measurement scheme, and represents an idealized environment.

We first generated a turbulent wind field with a length of 4192 s, a width and height of 128 m, and a mean wind speed of 20 m/s. Then, we calculated the REWS over a rotor disk of 126 m in the center of the wind field as mean over all longitudinal wind components. Further, we simulated a simplified lidar system measuring in two points 128 m in front of the rotor, 20 m to the right and to the left of the hub. From the two line-of-sight wind speeds we then calculated the lidar estimate of the REWS by assuming perfect alignment with the mean wind direction [5].

The first 30 s of the two signals are displayed in Figure 2(a). The REWS has less fluctuations compared to its lidar estimate, since the REWS corresponds to the wind speed spatially averaged over the rotor disk.

Figure 2: (a) Rotor effective wind speed (REWS) and its lidar estimate over time. (b) Coherence between the two signals from (a) over wave number and its theoretical value.

We then calculated the coherence between the reference and estimated REWS and compared it to its theoretical value [5], see Figure 2(b). The coherence from the simulation fits well to the theoretical value, which indicates that the simulation and wind field reconstruction was implemented correctly.

This first results will serve us as a basis for the next steps. For the considered combination of IEC Kaimal wind field and scan configuration, the baseline WFR represents the best theoretically possible result. Replacing the wind field by a more realistic (e.g. generated by LES) should give an idea of how much of the wind flow physics can be captured by the standard statistical turbulence mode within the baseline WFR. Finally, when reinforcing WFR with physics informed techniques by making use of simplified LES, we expect better preview of the real wind flow physics.

4 Outlook

We will first finish the steps of the 2D testing strategy described above. After these steps, we will extend the method to 3D and develop a similar testing strategy. An extension of the framework will include full aero-elastic simulations to evaluate the methods not only with respect to the wind preview quality, but also for their capability in improving wind turbine control.

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